

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Household Animal Stool Sample Collection	
Effective date: 01/07/19	Next Review Due:

Author	Signed	Date
Dr Derek Cocker		01/07/19

Reviewer	Signed	Date
Dr Nicholas Feasey		01/07/19
Authoriser	Signed	Date
Dr Nicholas Feasey		01/07/19

Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes made after pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable to the collection of animal stool samples from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL *E. coli* (ESBL-E) and ESBL *K. pneumoniae* (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

This method describes the process of collecting stool samples from animals present in and around the household, that will subsequently be screened for the presence of ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae* as part of the DRUM study.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Consent for the collection of animal stool
 - Collection of animal stool via stool collection pots and rectal swabs, according to this SOP
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Core Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM teleform LIMS system
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
- Study Laboratory Technicians

- Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
- Double-check correct sample labelling as in this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure field worker training in sample collection processes is provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of sample collection and processing.

4. Procedure

4.1. Materials and Equipment

Gloves

Blue topped sterile stool collection pots (with spoon inside)

Blue transwabs (rectal swabs)

Medical pulp bowls

Sterile collection bags

Hand disinfectant

4.2. Domestic Animal and Livestock Stool Collection (Sterile Pot)

Each animal species in and around the household should be identified and stool should be collected via collection of faecal matter from the floor. Inform the household members which animals have been selected for sampling and the method that will be used to obtain stool.

- 1) Gain verbal consent from the household for each animal sample that will be acquired.
- 2) Wear personal protective equipment throughout, including gloves and boots.
- 3) Domestic animals and livestock should have been pre-chosen. This will include: dogs, cats, cattle, sheep, goats and pigs. A total of 0-4 stool samples will be taken, and it is important to attempt to take stool from different species, prioritising domestic animals and livestock.
- 4) Animal stool will be identified by the field worker and corroborated by the household member. Fresh stool should preferentially be chosen.
- 5) Once identified, the field worker will use the spoon to collect the sample of stool from the floor and deposit it into the blue topped universal pot.

- 6) The aim is to collect as large a sample as possible, with a minimum of 2mls (although if only a smaller sample can be obtained this should be sent).
- 7) The stool sample should be clearly labelled with the species of animal from which the stool was taken and placed into a sealable plastic bag and placed into a container for transport to the laboratory (see 4.5).

4.3. Poultry Stool Collection (Cloacal swab)

Cloacal swabs should be collected on poultry. This includes all chickens, guinea fowl, ducks, geese and turkeys.

- 1) Gain verbal consent from the household for each animal sample that will be acquired.
- 2) Wear personal protective equipment throughout, including gloves and boots.
- 3) Open packaging, and appropriately restrain the animal
- 4) Insert the swab into rectum 1-1.5cm
- 5) Gently rotate swab
- 6) Remove and put swab into container
- 7) Label and place into a container for transport to the laboratory (see 4.5)

4.4 Gecko Stool Collection

Gecko stool can be obtained from droppings present within the household.

- 1) Wear personal protective equipment throughout collection, including gloves
- 2) Gain verbal consent from the household for collection
- 3) Characteristic excreta should be placed into sterile blue-topped stool containers
- 4) These stool pots should be labelled appropriately and placed into a container for transport to the laboratory (see 4.6)

4.5 Sample Storage and Transport

Protect all samples from direct sunlight and transport in an insulated container or refrigerator at 2 – 8°C. Samples should be analysed as soon as is practicable and storage under the above conditions should not exceed 24 h before the commencement of analysis.

5. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines

Collect 1 sample from **each** household animal. (*max 4 samples*)

Animal Stool Sampling in Household

Place samples in cool boxes for storage and transportation to the laboratory

Stool collected from the floor, taken by the field team

Cloacal Swab taken by the field team (*chickens only*)

Scan labels in laboratory reception

